

Seasonal variations of water quality parameters and their effect on the phytoplankton along a salinity in the Lake Naivasha-Oloiden

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Abstract

Lake Naivasha and Lake Oloiden merged leading to the formation of an estuary. This occurrence may affect the water quality and phytoplankton. A study was conducted with the objective: to investigate seasonal changes in the water quality parameters and their effect on phytoplankton. Depth and secchi depth were measured while some water quality parameters were measured *in situ* using YSI Multiparameter meter and water samples were collected for laboratory analysis of chlorophyll-a, phosphates, nitrates and total suspended solids. Phytoplankton sample was collected; identification and counting were done under a compound microscope. The nutrients, depth, secchi depth, temperature, dissolved oxygen, salinity, conductivity, total dissolved solids and pH varied monthly. All the water quality parameters positively correlated with *Chlorophyceae* in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden except dissolved oxygen, chlorophyll-a, depth and secchi depth that negatively correlated. There were seasonal changes in all the water quality parameters in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden except the total suspended solids whose effects were in Midlake There were seasonal changes in all the water quality parameters in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden except the total suspended solids whose effects were only in Midlake and Oloiden ST2. *Euglenophyceae*, *Bacillariophyceae* were not affected by water quality except the depth while the other families had varied effects from water quality in Lake Naivasha. All Lake Oloiden's phytoplankton families had varied effects from the water quality. Thus, the prevailing water quality affect phytoplankton.

Key words: estuary, Rainfall, phytoplankton

1.0 Introduction

There was an increase in the water level in Lake Naivasha; which was attributed to increased rainfall due to climate change (Nyangau, 2021). This phenomenon led to its merging with Lake Oloiden; which was previously separated by a papyrus reed (Ballot *et al.*, 2009). It resulted in the formation of a brackish water ecosystem. Mixing of saline and fresh water may lead to physical and chemical changes in the properties of water (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). Environmental and hydrographic parameters are important in the distribution of phytoplankton (Kathiresan, 2013).

Metabolic balance of an estuary is linked to biological diversity. There may be shift in the processes that take place due to conditions in an estuary e.g., photosynthesis and respiration; which may affect ecosystem metabolism. Its effects extend to the phytoplankton; since they are controlled by abiotic factors (Rochelle-Newall, 2011). Physico-chemical factors have a critical role in determining the assemblage of organisms (Okyere, 2018).

Climate change over the past has impacted most African lakes; leading to stratification. Lake Tanganyika has experienced the warming effect, water stability and decreased vertical mixing leading to reduction of nutrient loading in upper layers. Cyanophyceae blooms have been occurring during rainy season. Lakes Kivu, Edward and Malawi have experienced low phytoplankton diversity and biomass. Cyanophyceae dominance with seasonal Bacillariophyceae dominance have been noted in Lake Karibe while Lake Kivu has Bacillariophyceae dominance in high mixing period and Cyanophyceae dominance during stratified rainy season (Mzime *et al.*, 2010).

Water quality deteriorated previously in Lake Naivasha and it led to the shift in phytoplankton dominance: *Chlorophyceae* to *Cyanophyceae* while the salinity of Lake Oloiden increased shifting dominant family from *Cyanophyceae* to *Chlorophyceae* (Ballot *et al.*, 2009). The diversity and distribution of plankton may be influenced by hydrographic conditions that are specific to a locality (Kathiresan, 2013). There may be changes that occurred in water quality due to increased water level and formation of an estuary: which may impact phytoplankton. Thus, the objectives of the study to: (i) investigate seasonal changes in the water quality parameters and (ii) to determine the effect on water quality parameters on phytoplankton.

2.0 Materials and methods

2.1 Study site

The sampling was done monthly, for one year (August, 2020 to July, 2021) in the Lake Oloiden (00°50'S, 36°17'E) and Lake Naivasha (00°46'S, 36°22'E) along the salinity gradient (Ballot *et al.*, 2009). A transect was drawn from Oloiden ST1 to Malewa. Crescent and Korongo were added to those sites in the transect. Stratified random sampling design was used. The two lakes are close to the equator with a bimodal rainfall pattern (**Figure 1**) (Ndungu *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 1. A map of the study sites in the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden (Openstreetmap.org, 2021)

2.2 Water quality

The depth and secchi depth were measured using: a graduated rope that had a metallic end to enable straight drop and secchi disc (appearance and disappearance were recorded) respectively (Nyangu, 2021). Temperature, dissolved oxygen, total dissolved solids, conductivity, salinity and pH were measured *in situ* using YSI Multiparameter meter. Water samples were collected for laboratory analysis of total suspended solids (TSS), nutrients (nitrates and phosphates) and

Chlorophyll-a according to standard methods. Phosphates and orthophosphates were analyzed using: molybdenum blue ascorbic method and colorimetric methods respectively (APHA, 2005a). Chlorophyll-a was analyzed by Photometric absorbance method where readings were obtained at: 630nm, 647nm, 664nm and 750nm (wavelengths) and it was calculated using the formular below (APHA, 2005b).

$$Chl - \bar{a} = \frac{11.85(D_{664}-D_{750})-1.54(D_{647}-D_{750})-0.08(D_{630}-D_{750})*VE}{VS*\delta} \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

Where; D630, D647, D664, D750 are wavelengths 630nm, 647nm, 664nm and 750nm, VE was the volume of extract (ml), VS was the volume of filtered water sample and δ was the optical path length (cm) (Huang and Cong, 2007).

2.4 Phytoplankton

A van don sampler was used in picking the water sample which was sieved through a phytoplankton net (30 μm) and drops of Lugol iodine were added. Identification (using keys) and counting were done in Sedgewick Rafter cell, under a compound microscope (×100) (Bellinger, 2015). The phytoplankton density was calculated using the formular below.

$$D = \frac{N*V1}{V2} \dots\dots\dots (ii)$$

Where; D was Density (Ind/L), N was the average number of phytoplankton in a ml of the sample, V1 was average amount of volume of sample obtained (ml) and V2 was the volume of water filtered to obtain the sample (ml).

2.5 Statistical analysis

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was done for the of water quality variables (95% CI), further Turkey test was used. One tailed Pearson correlation was done in Statistical Package for Social Scientists. Phytoplankton density was calculated in R (version 4.3.1).

3.0 Results

3.1 Water quality

3.1.1 Depth

There was a significant difference in depth monthly in sites (P<0.05, **Figure 2**). Oloiden ST1 had the highest depth in November and lowest in June. October had the highest depth for Oloiden ST2

and Oseria while July and January had the lowest respectively. Korongo and Malewa's August had the highest depth while March's depth was the lowest.

Figure 2. The lake depth in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden (Error bar= SE).

3.1.2 Secchi depth

Secchi depth had significant differences with respect with months in the various sites ($P < 0.05$, Figure 3). Oloiden ST1 had the highest March secchi depth and the lowest in August. Oloiden ST2, Oseria, Crescent had highest secchi depth in November (Malewa's lowest) while September, April and June had the lowest respectively.

Figure 3. The secchi depth in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Oloiden and Naivasha (Error bar =SE)

3.1.3 Temperature

Temperature was significantly different (monthly) ($P < 0.05$, **Figure 4**); December had the highest temperature for Oloiden ST1, Oseria and Crescent while July and August had the lowest respectively. Oloiden ST2, Korongo and Malewa had the lowest temperature in July (Midlake's highest) while the highest was in November, January and April respectively.

Figure 4. The temperature in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden

3.1.4 Dissolved oxygen

All study sites had significant differences in dissolved oxygen (DO) with respect to months: it was highest in September for Oloiden ST1, ST2, Crescent and Malewa and lowest in June, November (Korongo's highest) and February (Midlake's lowest) respectively (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. The dissolved oxygen in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden.

3.1.5 Conductivity

Conductivity was significantly different monthly ($P < 0.05$, **Figure 6**): its lowest was in August for Oseria, Korongo and Midlake while their highest was in January and June respectively. Oloiden ST1 and Malewa had the lowest conductivity in September while the highest was in March (Oloiden ST2's highest) and April (Crescent's lowest) respectively.

Figure 6. The conductivity in the various months and study sites of the Lakes Oloiden and Naivasha

3.1.6 Total dissolved solids

There were significant differences in the total dissolved solids (TDS) monthly ($P < 0.05$, **Figure 7**): Oloiden ST1 and ST2 had the highest TDS in July and the lowest was in October (Oseria's lowest) and September respectively. March had the highest TDS Crescent, Korongo and Malewa while September, August (Midlake's highest) and October were the lowest respectively.

Figure 7. The total dissolved solids in the various months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden

3.1.7 Salinity

All study sites had significant differences in salinity monthly ($P < 0.05$): the highest was in June and July while the lowest in Oloiden ST2 and Korongo was October; Oloiden ST1 and Malewa had September; Oseria had August while Crescent had March (**Figure 8**). There was a significant difference between the study sites salinity ($P < 0.05$). Oloiden ST1 salinity was distinct similar to Oloiden ST2; and then, all other sites (Lake Naivasha) were similar (Tukey test). Oloiden ST1's salinity was lower than Oloiden ST2 (312ppm) which had the highest salinity and a decrease was noted in Oseria. Oloiden ST2 had a 3.5 times higher salinity as compared to Oseria.

Figure 8. The salinity in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden

3.1.8 pH

pH had significant differences with respect to months (Figure 9): Oseria, Korongo and Malewa had the highest in March (Oloiden ST2's lowest) and the lowest in July, June and September respectively. Oloiden ST1's pH was highest in February and lowest in November (vice versa for Midlake).

Figure 9. The pH in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden

3.1.9 Nitrates

The nitrates were significantly different monthly (**Figure 10**): all sites had January as the highest and March as the lowest (except Midlake and Korongo; that had July and May respectively).

Figure 10. The nitrates in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden.

3.1.10 Phosphates

Phosphates were significantly different with respect to months in the various study sites ($P < 0.05$, **Figure 11**); Crescent and Midlake were highest in September and lowest in April and July (Malewa's lowest) respectively.

Figure 11. The phosphates in the respective months and study sites of Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden

3.1.11 Chlorophyll-a

Chlorophyll-a had significant differences with respect to months in the various study sites ($P < 0.05$, **Figure 12**): Oloiden ST1 had highest in July and lowest in December (Crescent's highest). Korongo's was highest in June and lowest in September.

Figure 12. The chlorophyll-a in the respective months and study sites of the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden

3.1.12 Total suspended solids

The total suspended solids (TSS) were significant differences with respect to months ($P < 0.05$) in some study sites: Oloiden ST2's August and November (Midlake's lowest) had the highest while May and February had the lowest (**Figure 13**).

Figure 13. The total suspended solids in the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden respective study sites with respect to months

3.2 Phytoplankton density

Chlorophyceae (Chloro) had the highest number of species (15) (Table 1). *Bacillariophyceae* (Bac) and *Cyanophyceae* (Cyano) had 4 species; *Dinophyceae* (Dino) and *Euglenophyceae* (Eugleno) had 3 species while *Rhodophyceae* (Rhodo) had 1 species. There was variation in abundance in the lakes and respective study sites.

Table 1. The density of various phytoplankton and species in the respective study sites of Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden (results were rounded off to the nearest thousand; K=1000).

	Oloiden ST1	Oloiden ST2	Oseria	Crescent	Korongo	Midlake	Malewa
<i>Bacillariophyceae</i>							
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>			30K	45K	44K	37.1K	47.6K
<i>Nitzschia</i> sp.			16K		13K	21K	27.3K
<i>Navicula subtilissima</i>			2K	3.1K	2.1K	2K	2.1K
<i>Tetracyclus</i> sp.	2K	3.2K	18K	27K	17K	19.2K	22.2K
<i>Chlorophyceae</i>							
<i>Surrirella elegans</i>	1.6K	2.2K	4.3K	8.1K		1K	1.4K
<i>Surrirella linearis</i>	11K	11K	2.2K				
<i>Chlorella</i> sp.		5.3K		2K	3.5K	5.4K	1.7K
<i>Crucigenia tetrapedia</i>	2K	2.2K	1.3K	2K	2.8K		
<i>Scenedesmus communis</i>		1K	1.7K	4.6K	1K	1.3K	2.4K

<i>Scenedesmus opoliensis</i>	3.4K	7.3K	4K	2.5K		1K		
<i>Scenedesmus accuminatus</i>	22K	15K						
<i>Spirogyra prolecta</i>			2.3K	4.6K	2.8K	8.1K	1.4K	
<i>Pediastrum v. boryanum</i>	24K	18K	3K	4.1K	2.1K	2K	2.8K	
<i>Pediastrum boryanum</i>	2.4K	1.6K	2K	2K	2.4K	2K	2.1K	
<i>Pediastrum duplex</i>	11K		1.7K	4.6K	2.1K	1.7K	2.8K	
<i>Pediastrum simplex</i>				3.1K	1.4K	1K	2.4K	
<i>Tetraedron</i> sp.			4K	1.5K				
<i>Tetmorus</i> sp.			1.3K	25K				
<i>Oocytis</i> sp.							2.1K	
<i>Cyanophyceae</i>								
<i>Anabaena circunalis</i>	2K	1.9K	4.3K	5.1K	4.4K	3.4K	2.1K	
<i>Athrospira</i> sp.	2K		1.7K	2K	1.7K	1K	1.7K	
<i>Cylindrospermum</i> sp.			21K	33K	14K		12.5K	
<i>Microsistis</i> sp.			9.3K	10.2K	5.2K	4.7K	6.2K	
<i>Dinophyceae (Din)</i>								
<i>Ceratium hirundinella</i>	8.4K	7.9K	4K			12K	5.6K	
<i>Ceratium cornutum</i>					56K			
<i>Lepocinclis</i> sp.			1.7K	3.1K	2K	1.3K		
<i>Euglenophyceae</i>								
<i>Euglena mutabilis</i>	8	8.3K	2K	2.5K	3.1K	2K	1.4K	
<i>Phacus helicoides</i>								
<i>Peridinium cinctum</i>	5.7K	4.8K	1.7K		4.9K			
<i>Rhodophyceae</i>								
<i>Hildenbrandia</i> sp.				1,827K	363K	593K	437K	396K

3.3 Correlation

3.3.1 Lake Naivasha

Salinity, conductivity and chlorophyll-a had a significant positive correlation with *Rhodophyceae* (Table 2). *Euglenophyceae*, *Bacillariophyceae* and *Dinophyceae* correlated positively with the depth and later negatively correlated with temperature, DO and pH (P=0.05*, P=0.01**). *Cyanophyceae* positively correlated with temperature, DO and nitrates; its correlation was negative with depth. All water quality parameters positively correlated with *Chlorophyceae* except; DO, chlorophyll-a, depth and secchi-D's correlation that was negative.

Table 2. Pearson’s correlation of phytoplankton families in Lake Naivasha with water quality parameters (Temp=temperature, Cond=Conductivity, Sal=salinity, Chl-a=Chlorophyll-a, Nitrates=NO₃⁻, Phosphates=PO₄³⁺ Secchi depth=SD, and D=Depth).

3.3.2 Lake Oloiden

The conductivity, TDS, salinity, pH, temperature, nitrates, phosphates and TSS had a positive correlation with *Euglenophyceae*, *Chlorophyceae* and *Cyanophyceae* while secchi depth, depth and DO’s was negative (although chlorophyll-a correlated positively and negatively respectively). Temperature, conductivity, TDS, salinity, PH, nitrates, phosphates and TSS’s correlation with *Dinophyceae* was negative while DO, chlorophyll-a and depth's correlation was positive. The DO and conductivity had a positive correlation with the *Bacillariophyceae* and a negative correlation with temperature, TDS, salinity and pH (Table 3).

Table 3. Pearson’s correlation of phytoplankton families in Lake Oloiden with water quality parameters.

	Temp	DO	Cond	TDS	Sal	pH	Chl-a	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁺	D	SD	TSS
Eugleno	1**	-1**	1**	1**	1**	1**	1**	1**	1**	-1**	-1**	1**
Dino	-1**	1**	-1**	-1**	-1**	-1**	1**	-1**	-1**	1**	1**	-1**
Cyano	1**	-1**	1**	1*	1**	1**	-1**	1**	1**	-1**	-1**	1**
Chloro	1**	-1**	1**	1**	1*	1**	-1**	1**	1**	-1**	-1**	1**
Bac	-1**	1**	1**	-1**	-1**	-1**	1**	-1**	-1**	1**	1*	-1**

	Temp	DO	Cond	TDS	Sal	pH	Chl-a	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁺	D	SD	TSS
Rhodo	0.6	0.6	0.8*	0.8	0.9*	0.8	0.9*	0.5	-0.6	-0.6	-0.4	-0.4
Eugleno	-0.5	-0.5	-0.3	-0.2	-0.9	-0.6	-0.5	-0.5	-0.2	0.8*	-0.3	-0.2
Dino	-0.8*	-0.8*	-0.6	-0.6	-0.5	-0.8*	-0.7	-0.7	0.3	0.8*	-0.6	0.1
Cyano	0.8*	0.8*	0.4	0.4	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.7*	0.2	-0.9**	0.1	0.3
Chloro	0.5	0.4	0.8*	0.7*	0.8*	0.5	0.6	0.5	-0.5	-0.3	-0.3	-0.3
Bac	0.3	0.4	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.6	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.8*	0.5	0.00

4.0 Discussion

The water level rose in the Lake Naivasha and Lake Oloiden whose depth used to be: 4-6m and 3-5m respectively (Hubble and Harper, 2002; Mavuti and Harper, 2005). Oloiden ST1 had the highest depth in the short rainy season and the lowest in long dry season while Oloiden ST2 and

Oseria had their highest in long dry season and lowest in long rainy and short dry season respectively. Korongo and Malewa had their shortest depth in short dry season and longest depth in short rainy season. Secchi depth increased as compared to previous findings (Ndungu, 2014). Oloiden ST2, Oseria and Crescent's secchi depth were the highest in the short rainy season (lowest in Malewa) and lowest in the long dry and long rainy season respectively. The secchi depth was highest during short dry season and lowest in long dry season for Oloiden ST1. The seasons may impact the secchi depth. Temperature was similar to previous research findings (Ndungu *et al.*, 2014). Oloiden ST1, Oseria and Crescent had the highest temperature in the short rainy season while the lowest was in the long dry season. Oloiden ST2, Korongo and Malewa's temperatures were lowest in the long rainy season (Midlake's highest) and highest in the short rainy, short dry and long rainy season respectively. Seasons may have an effect on temperature; decrease was noted in the long rainy season (Ndungu *et al.*, 2014).

Dissolved oxygen was lower than previous data (Ballot *et al.*, 2009). Oloiden ST1, ST2, Crescent and Malewa had their highest DO in the long dry season while their lowest were in the long rainy, short rainy (Korongo's highest) and short dry season (Midlake's lowest) respectively. Conductivity was much lower than previous findings; which was associated with dilution due to water level rise (Ballot *et al.*, 2009). Oloiden ST1 and Malewa had the highest conductivity in the long dry season while the lowest was in the short dry (Oloiden ST2's highest) and long rainy season (Crescent's lowest) respectively. Oseria, Korongo and Midlake had the highest conductivity in the short dry season while the lowest was in long dry season: seasons may have an effect on the conductivity. Its increase led to an increase in the salinity and pH in the Lake Oloiden (Ndungu *et al.*, 2014)

In comparison to previous TDS findings; the present were lower; which may be attributed to dilution effect due to water level rise. Oloiden ST1 and ST2 had the highest TDS in the long rainy season and the lowest in the long dry season (Oseria's lowest). The Crescent, Korongo and Malewa had their highest TDS in the short dry season while the long dry season was the lowest (Midlake's highest) (Ndungu *et al.*, 2014). An increase in TDS led to an increase in the pH in the Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden (Ballot *et al.*, 2009).

The salinity gradient exists where the fresh water in Oseria mixes with the saline water in Oloiden ST2 and the ratio was (1:3.5). A slight increase was noted in the salinity of Oloiden ST2 which was distinct: similarly, Oloiden ST1 was distinct; with all the Lake Naivasha sites being similar

and distinct together. Slight increase at Oloiden ST2 could be associated with non-linear variation in an estuarine environment (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). The gradient decreased from Lake Oloiden to the Lake Naivasha. Salinity was highest in all the sites in long rainy season and lowest were: long dry (Oloiden ST1, Oseria, Korongo and Malewa) and short dry (Crescent) seasons. pH was lower than previous findings; attributed to dilution (Ballot et al., 2009). Oloiden ST1 had the highest pH in the short dry season and the lowest in the short rainy season (Midlake's vice versa). Oseria, Korongo and Malewa had their highest pH in the short dry season (Oloiden ST2 's lowest) while their lowest was in long rainy and long dry season respectively (Ndungu *et al.*, 2014).

Nitrates were higher than the previous findings in Lake Naivasha which may be associated with agricultural runoff from the catchment (Ndungu *et al.*, 2014). All the sites' nitrates were high starting short dry season which may have coincided with the agricultural activities and lower at end of short dry season (except Midlake's and Korongo's whose lowest was during long rainy season). The phosphates were similar to previous findings in Lake Naivasha (Obegi *et al.*, 2021). Phosphates increased in the long dry season in Crescent and Midlake and decreased in the long rainy season (also Malewa's lowest). Oloiden ST1 had their highest phosphates in the long rainy season and their lowest in the short rainy season (Crescent's highest). Korongo had the highest in long rainy season and lowest in long dry season. Chlorophyll-a was similar to previous finding in Lake Naivasha and it has generally decreased with the water level rise. High chlorophyll-a was observed during the long rainy season; could be associated with surface runoff (nitrates were high after the rainy season). Long dry and short rainy season (Midlake's lowest) had the highest while short dry and long rainy season had the lowest chlorophyll-a in Oloiden ST1. The TSS were lower than previous findings (Lake Naivasha) which was attributed to dilution. Long dry season and short rainy season had the highest chlorophyll-a for Oloiden ST2 (Midlake's lowest) and their lowest was in the short dry and long rainy season (Ndungu et al., 2014).

Lake Oloiden's *Bacillariophyceae* increased consequently with conductivity and DO and decreased with increase in; pH, salinity, TDS and temperature. *Tetracyclus* sp. had high abundance in Oloiden ST1 and ST2.; whose conductivity, pH, salinity, TDS and temperature were high. Lake Naivasha's *Bacillariophyceae* increased with depth increment: Crescent's had the highest abundance of *Aulacoseira granulata* (highest density in Lake Naivasha, signifying a eutrophic condition), *tetracyclus* sp. and *Cylindrospermum* sp. (Ballot *et al.*, 2009).

Salinity, chlorophyll-a and conductivity increased with *Rhodophyceae*. *Hildenbrandia* sp. was highest in Oseria: could have been influenced by estuarine condition (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). *Euglenophyceae* increased with depth increment in Lake Naivasha; contrary to its low density in the deepest site. It increased with all water quality increment except; DO, depth and secchi depth in Lake Oloiden. *Euglena mutabilis* had the highest density in Oloiden ST1 and ST2 (density was greater than Oseria's and yet both were estuarine: exhibition of non-linear variation) (Nielson *et al.*, 2003; Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010).

Dinophyceae increased with depth increment and decreased with the increase in temperature, pH and DO in the Lake Naivasha. *Lepocinlis* sp. was highest in Crescent. Its presence was indicative of organic matter presence (Ndungu, 2014). Temperature, conductivity, TDS, salinity, PH, nitrates, phosphates and TSS increased with the decreased in the *Dinophyceae* (Lake Oloiden) and increased with DO, chlorophyll-a and depth increment. Variables that had a negative effect were high in Lake Oloiden; results contrary to previous findings. *Ceratium hirundinella* density was high in Oloiden ST1 and ST2 (density was lower compared to Oseria's; exhibiting non-linear variation in an estuary) (Olofson *et al.*, 2020). Phytoplankton (proxy of chlorophyll-a); photosynthesize releasing oxygen which may have led to increase in DO (Ndungu, 2014).

Cyanophyceae increased with DO, nitrates and temperature and decreased with increase in depth in Lake Naivasha. On contrary, *Anabaena circunalis* of Crescent was the highest. Although, it increased with the increase in: conductivity, TDS, pH, salinity, temperature, nitrates, phosphates and TSS in Lake Oloiden. *Anabaena circunalis* was high in Oloiden ST1 and low in Oloiden ST2. The salinity, pH, TDS and conductivity positive effect was contrary to Nielson *et al.* (2003). Temperature influences photosynthetic activity of phytoplankton (Velasco *et al.*, 2019).

All the water quality parameters increased with *Chlorophyceae* except chlorophyll-a, DO, secchi-D and depth in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden. *Spirogyra prolecta* was highest in Midlake while *Pediastrum duplex* was high in ST1. *Scenedesmus accuminatus* was only present in Oloiden ST1 and ST2 and its density was high, similar to *Pediastrum v. boryanum*. All the sites in Lake Naivasha had a low abundance except Oseria whose productivity was higher (Telesh and Khelebivich, 2010). A high TSS (could be due to phytoplankton; they contribute to turbidity) and transport organic matter (with nutrients) which may lead to increase in the phytoplankton/chlorophyll-a; which contribute to decrease in secchi depth and at their decomposition consume DO (Ndungu, 2014).

5.0 Conclusion

There were seasonal changes in all the water quality parameters in Lakes Naivasha and Oloiden except the total suspended solids whose effects were only in Midlake and Oloiden ST2. *Euglenophyceae*, *Bacillariophyceae* were not affected by water quality except the depth while the other families had varied effects from water quality in Lake Naivasha. All Lake Oloiden's phytoplankton families had varied effects from the water quality. Thus, the prevailing water quality affect phytoplankton.

6.0 Acknowledgement

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